

Continuous Volitional Control of a Bionic Leg Supports Diverse Walking Patterns in both AMI and Bone-Anchored Prosthesis Users

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ABSTRACT

Myoelectric control paradigms have the potential to enable continuous volitional control of bionic limbs in various movement conditions. Although individuals with agonist-antagonist muscle interface (AMI) amputation were proven to display a greater degree of continuous volitional control in bionic ankle-foot systems with respect to conventional socket-suspended prosthetic users, it remains unclear how myoelectric interfaces could translate to non-AMI prosthetic users with bone-anchored prostheses (BAP). This study proposes a human-machine interface (HMI) based on a neuromechanical model to enable volitional, continuous control of a bionic leg in AMI and BAP users, walking across various speeds and ground inclinations. Differently from state of the art solutions, the proposed method is based on a digital twin of the intact contralateral leg, synthesizing the user's phantom limb musculoskeletal function as controlled by muscle activations measured from the stump. When embedded in a real-time framework, it enabled the participants to achieve volitional modulation of peak muscle activation timing and amplitude during overground walking at three speeds (between 1.6 and 3.96 km/h).

Moreover, case studies are provided during calf-raises (30, 45, and 60 bpm) and ramp ascent walking (3 and 5 % incline). Before prosthesis control tests, the participants underwent a 2-day gait training session; results showed that all three subjects learned how to alter initial muscle activation patterns so that an average of 87% of peak activation timing fell within target ranges. The proposed neuromechanical modeling technology opens new avenues toward generalizable HMI for the volitional control of active prostheses beyond set conditions and subjects.

Keywords: Biomechanics, Electromyography, Control systems, Legs, AMI, BAP

1 INTRODUCTION

Human movement underlies interaction and coordination across nervous, muscular, and skeletal systems. Thousands of micro-scale neural structures, such as spinal motor neurons are recruited to form the final neural code instructing skeletal muscles how to contract for the execution of a movement (1; 2).

Recruited fibers collectively generate mechanical forces, which are subsequently transferred via series-elastic tendons to the skeletal system, thereby accelerating biological joints (1). These neuro-muscular mechanisms are key for producing the broad range of biological joint torques that accelerate anatomical limbs and enable functional movements such as locomotion across different speeds (3; 4). A transtibial

amputation disrupts the neuromuscular pathways underlying the closed-loop control of the ankle muscles (5). However, motorized prostheses (or bionic limbs), are emerging as a viable solution to restore the biomechanical function of the missing limb (6). A key challenge lies in designing human-machine interfaces that allow individuals who underwent diverse types of amputation procedures to gain volitional control of their bionic limbs, as a natural extension of their own body in a task-agnostic manner (6; 7). Despite advances in EMG-based control and surgical techniques like targeted muscle reinnervation (TMR) and the agonist-antagonist muscle interface (AMI), bionic legs remain limited in clinical and commercial impact (8; 9; 10; 11). Most controllers rely on rule-based algorithms, such as finite state machines, to pre-define impedance properties based on detected motor tasks and gait phases (6). However, these predefined behaviors often fail to match actual movement demands and do not allow users to continuously modulate torque in response to changes in speed, terrain, or perturbations (12; 10).

Human intent recognition for bionic legs has primarily relied on surface EMGs in the form of classifiers, offering a viable way to interface with the neuromuscular system (6; 13). While EMG classifiers can detect discrete locomotion modes, they limit the user's ability to volitionally control limb dynamics in real time (14; 15).

Myoelectric solutions were proposed for the continuous and proportional control of bionic leg plantar-dorsiflexion during walking, stair climbing (16) or perturbed standing (14; 17), with bionic leg dorsiflexion being automatically engaged when the participant's plantarflexor muscles relaxed (18; 19). Recent work utilized EMG signals from an AMI established between residual stump tibialis anterior and gastrocnemius muscles, to estimate a target joint position and impedance, while modulating maximum joint torques based on joint angle and velocity (20).

More recent studies have explored continuous myoelectric control outside laboratory environments, demonstrating that transtibial amputees with socket-suspended bionic legs could volitionally activate their residual limb muscles to control bionic ankle in real-world settings (21).

However, while bionic leg users who underwent the AMI surgery, have so far displayed increased degree of volitional myoelectric control across various locomotion tasks (20), with respect to non-AMI individuals with traditional socket-suspended prostheses (18; 22; 21), it remains unclear how myoelectric control paradigms for bionic legs would translate to non-AMI bionic leg users with bone-anchored prostheses (BAP) (23; 24). In BAP individuals, the absence of the suspended socket, would prevent onset of stump muscle contractions aimed at socket stabilization, which would yield to sub-optimal muscle activation for myoelectric controllers (25). Moreover, BAP users have displayed improved walking performance, with faster walking speeds, with respect to conventional non-BAP, socket-suspended prosthetic users (25). Differently from AMI-amputees, in BAP-amputees sensory feedback from the muscles is not restored. However, the stump muscle integrity is usually preserved, unlike conventional non-AMI and non-BAP socket-suspended amputees.

In this paper, we propose a myoelectric human-bionic-leg interface based on an EMG-driven neuromechanical model, hereafter referred to as the neuromechanical model-based control (NMBC) (26). Specifically, we investigate how NMBC could be used to enable continuous and volitional myoelectric control of bionic legs across locomotion speeds and ground-inclines in three individuals with transtibial amputation with AMI and BAP procedures respectively *i.e.*, in two individuals who underwent the AMI surgical procedure that used a socket-suspended bionic leg (9; 27; 28; 29) and in one individual who used BAP bionic leg with a press-fit osseointegration implant (BADAL X OTI, OTN Implants BV) (30).

The proposed NMBC relies on real-time musculoskeletal models of the phantom limb, which are used to convert stump muscle EMGs into bionic limb torque commands (31). This allows for the continuous EMG decoding of biomechanically plausible joint torques, which enable the bionic leg to closely mimic the biomechanical function of intact limbs during dynamic weight-bearing locomotion (speeds between 1.6 and 3.96 km/h and 0, 3 and 5 % inclines). Differently, from state of the art work, the proposed NMBC incorporates a musculoskeletal model of the phantom limb, which was created as the digital copy of the participant's intact contralateral limb (31). That is, NMBC's person- and leg-specific musculoskeletal model captured multiple biomechanical properties of the participant's intact leg including limb anthropometry, and musculoskeletal geometry as well as the force-generating capacity of the major muscle-tendon units (MTUs) spanning the ankle joint.

Previous studies have employed various approaches to calibrate musculoskeletal models, yet none have directly aimed at identifying an individual's physiological parameters. Several studies rely on the normalization of EMGs alone, which in turn is used to modulate the setpoint of a variable of interest (21; 18).

Other studies have explicitly utilized musculoskeletal models to generate prosthesis commands (7; 22), leveraging simulated muscles and skeletal geometries to determine joint-level torques. In (22), the musculoskeletal model is calibrated for each individual using a simulated reflex model that incorporates the participant's body characteristics. In contrast, (7) derives muscle parameters through data-driven optimization based on healthy individuals.

Our results showed that, following a 2-day visual feedback-based training, the proposed approach allowed for the fully volitional control of a motorized ankle bionic leg, simultaneously in plantar and dorsiflexion, across weight-bearing walking at three speeds (Results Section) and two incline levels (Supplementary Materials). Results showed that bionic limb volitional control could be achieved throughout the entire movement cycle with no need to use *a priori* defined finite state machines.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Experimental protocol

We enrolled three male participants (Subject 1-AMI: weight 103 Kg, height 196 cm; Subject 2-AMI: height 189 cm, weight 85 Kg; Subject 3-BAP: height 185 cm, weight 85 Kg), with below-knee amputation, who volunteered for this investigation and gave their informed written consent. Subject 1-AMI underwent an AMI surgical procedure (9) combined with TSR (8) of the medial skin of the residual limb by the sural nerve to restore sensation of the foot sole; Subject 2-AMI underwent an AMI surgical procedure and, Subject 3-BAP underwent an osseointegration procedure. The project was approved by the Central Committee on Research Involving Human Subjects (Ministry of Health, Welfare and Sport of Oost-Nederland - WMO), dossier number NL81380.091.22.

The protocol involved a 3-day session at the University of Twente (Enschede, The Netherlands). Figure 1 gives an overview of the real-time walking at ground elevation, an example of the full protocol is described in detail in Supplementary Materials.

Day 1 was dedicated to the bionic leg alignment, the selection of adequate positions of the electrodes, and the first training on how to use the myoelectric controller (Video S5, Fig. 3). We placed 8 monopolar electrodes on both muscle bellies of the gastrocnemius (GM) and tibialis anterior (TA). In the case of Subject 3-BAP, only 4 electrodes were placed since the stump was smaller (Fig. 1). Further, we selected one pair of electrodes that yielded a bi-polar signal and we chose one signal channel per muscle by analyzing the activities of each group during walking. Days 1 and 2 were dedicated to the training of the participant while walking at their preferred speed. A graphical user interface (GUI) based on previous research (18) provided the participant with visual feedback of one of his muscle activations at a time over the gait cycle, alternating sessions with GM feedback with sessions with TA feedback. The participant was instructed to follow a reference profile for the GM and TA muscles individually. Reference profiles were derived from our previous work on human locomotion and muscle modularity (32), which were adjusted in amplitude and peak time to best match his preferred pattern. On day 1, each user performed the trials with the passive prosthesis. On day 2, Subjects 2-AMI and 3-BAP could already experience the active bionic leg. Data collected on the training of day 1 were employed in creating the participant-specific neuromechanical model (*i.e.*, muscle activations, leg joint angles, and reference ankle joint torques from the intact limb). See Section Materials and Methods - Model calibration for more details on the model calibration procedure. Day 3 focused on the actual trial, where each subject was challenged to complete varied trials with the bionic leg driven by a personalized NMBC:

1. **Subject 1-AMI** performed calf-raises while following the cadence of a metronome at 3 different frequencies (30, 45, and 60 beats per minute (bpm) - Video S2, S3, Figure S5) and, ground-level treadmill walking at 3 different speeds (1.6 km/h, 2km/h, and 2.4 km/h - Video S1, Figure 2)
2. **Subject 2-AMI** performed ground-level treadmill walking at 3 different speeds(1.98 km/h, 2.34km/h, and 2.69 km/h - Video S6, Figure 2), and treadmill walking at preferred speed at three different ground inclinations (ground, 3% and 5% - Video S7, Figure S3).
3. **Subject 3-BAP** performed ground-level treadmill walking at 3 different speeds (2.52 km/h, 3.24 km/h, and 3.96 km/h - Video S8, Figure 2), and treadmill walking at preferred speed at three different ground inclinations (ground, 3%, and 5% - Video S9, Figure S3).

Figure 1. Weight-bearing treadmill walking at three different speeds was performed. Two of the eight bipolar channels placed on top of both TA and GM were selected to drive the neuromusculoskeletal model (more details in the Materials and Methods section). Joint angles from the prosthesis were fed back to update the kinematic-dependent states of the neuromusculoskeletal model (e.g., muscle-tendon unit length and moment arms), which outputs reference control torques to the prosthesis low-level controller (more details in section Materials and Methods - Software and Hardware Control Pipeline).

2.2 Software and Hardware Control Pipeline

An active ankle bionic leg capable of plantarflexion and dorsiflexion (EMPOWER, Ottobock SE & Co. KGaA, Duderstadt, Germany), operated in current control mode and therefore received motor current commands. The maximum allowed current was equivalent to a torque of 50 Nm or 70 Nm in isometric conditions at the neutral foot position. An embedded interface hardware (NUCLEO-F767ZI, STMicroelectronics, Geneva, Switzerland, and netSHIELD NSHIELD 52-RE, Hilscher Gesellschaft für System automation mbH, Hattersheim am Main, Germany) converted incoming torque commands into current setpoints by dividing them by the motor constant (k_t) adjusted by the motor-to-joint gear ratio. The embedded interface received commands through an Ethernet for Control Automation Technology (EtherCAT) communication protocol. The embedded hardware was also responsible for making available internal data from the bionic leg, such as joint angles. A workstation (Windows 10 Pro) ran a communication and processing master (TwinCAT, Beckhoff Automation GmbH & Co. KG, Verl, Germany) as well as a neuro-musculoskeletal toolbox (CEINMS-RT (33)), responsible for simulating the muscle model of the participant, which in turn generated torque setpoints.

Data collected during the experiment except for marker data, as described in the section Data Collection, were also aggregated into the TwinCAT master.

Additional software running in the TwinCAT master was also capable of offsetting setpoint torques to the bionic leg. Such offsets moved torque biases as outputs of the muscle model back to zero.

2.3 Neuromechanical Modeling

We used the open-source CEINMS-RT platform previously developed by the authors to create the NMBC mid-level bionic leg controller incorporating a musculoskeletal ankle model based (2; 34; 26; 33). This consisted of a personalized (see section Model calibration) EMG-driven-musculoskeletal model capable of online predicting joint torques (33). Supplementary material includes a detailed schematic of the control pipeline designed for the bionic leg (see Figure S1). Briefly, real-time muscle activation signals were filtered (see Section Online Data Processing Pipeline) and normalized based on a maximal

voluntary contraction (MVC) value that was extracted while each participant was instructed to generate maximal contractions during a sitting trial and a standing trial. The recorded muscle activation from GM drove 3 MTUs in the model (stage B, Figure S1): GM, GL, and SO, which were found to be synergistic (32). Muscle activations of the TA drove the respective MTU in the model. The internal encoder of the bionic leg provided the ankle joint angles, which were used as input to cubic B-splines, derived from a participant-specific OpenSim geometry model (stage C, Figure S1) (35). Joint angle-driven B-splines were used to compute MTU's musculotendon length (LMT) as well as moment arms (MA)(36). The knee joint was assumed to be fully extended.

Finally, in stage D - Figure S1, the muscle activation signals and MTU lengths were used to compute the muscle-tendon forces using a Hill-type model(37; 38).

The joint torque at the ankle was the result of the projection of MTU forces via MA (stage E - Figure S1).

2.4 NMBC calibration

The open-source software OpenSim (39) was utilized to adjust a generic model of musculoskeletal geometry (34) to match each participant's anthropometric data.

We employed a generic full-body model of the musculoskeletal geometry to represent the participant's anthropometry (gait2392 model (39)). Joint positions, center of mass, force application points, muscles, and ligament attachment points were linearly scaled according to the distances between the experimental and virtual markers (34). Although the full-body model was scaled, the calibration procedure involved 4 MTUs and 1 degree of freedom (DOF) around the ankle joint.

Muscle activations from the stump, inverse kinematics resolved for 3-dimensional ankle joint angles, and, joint moments, referred to as "experimental reference joint moments", are the input data required by the NMBC optimization algorithm (34). Ankle dorsiflexion torques from the inverse dynamic calculations were artificially increased during the early swing for the calibration to account for the additional torque required to overcome the friction of the bionic leg joint, which was in turn magnified by the transmission ratio of the actuation mechanism. The first positive half cycle of a sinusoidal curve was added to the experimental joint moment (65-85% gait phase) with an amplitude of 15Nm.

The calibration of NMBC's inner muscle model force-generating parameters was based on two optimization steps, which enabled the identification of MTU parameters that vary non-linearly with individuals' anthropometries (33). In the first optimization step, we derived initial values for tendon slack lengths and optimal fiber lengths within each modeled MTU. This was done as previously described to preserve normalized values between generic and linearly scaled musculoskeletal geometries (40).

In the second optimization step, an extended parameter set was calibrated including the MTU excitation-to-activation shape factor, MTU strength coefficients, tendon slack length, and, optimal fiber length.

A simulated annealing algorithm was used to vary the above-listed parameters, minimizing the sum of the mean square differences between the predicted and experimental joint moments calculated over all calibration trials (34).

2.5 Data collection

A motion capture system provided marker data in 3D space (Oqus, Qualisys, Sweden), and an instrumented treadmill provided 3-dimensional forces, torques, and center of pressure (M-Gait, MotekForce Link, The Netherlands). EMG signals were collected by 8 bipolar channels placed along 2 muscles (GM, TA) on the stump (4 for Subject 3-BAP). To guarantee user comfort with the socket in place, we used disposable adhesive gel electrodes (disposable adhesive 4-disk electrodes from Technomed Europe) and Myoplus amplifiers (Myoplus, Ottobock, Germany). Each muscle was instrumented with 4 (2 for Subject 3-BAP) bipolar channels, but only the muscle activation channel that represented a unilateral contraction with the least noise level was used for control.

2.6 Data Processing

Online data refers to the data available during the experiments, which informs the control of the bionic leg. Offline data, on the other hand, were logged and analyzed after the experiment. All data produced in the present study are available upon reasonable request to the authors.

2.6.1 Online Data Processing Pipeline

EMG data passed through a Butterworth band-pass filter of cutoff frequencies 30 and 300 Hz, then their absolute value was taken, and finally, the envelope was determined by filtering it with a Butterworth 2nd

order low-pass filter with a cutoff frequency of 3Hz. Prosthesis angle data were filtered by a Butterworth 2nd order low-pass filter with a cutoff frequency of 3Hz. The delivered torques were limited to 50 and 70 Nm. This limit was set as a safety measure implemented due to software constraints. In particular, no measures were in place to prevent the hardware end-stops from being reached during active control, which in turn could cause physical damage to the bionic leg. A software constraint was implemented for Subject 3-BAP's experiment and the torque limit was increased to 70Nm.

This limitation affected the amount of support generated by the bionic leg during push-off.

2.6.2 Offline Data Processing Pipeline

Marker data were preprocessed within the manufacturer's proprietary software (QTM, Qualisys, Sweden), where marker gaps were filled, and subsequently, data were exported and loaded into MATLAB (The MathWorks Inc., United States). Marker and ground reaction force (GRF) data were filtered by a fourth-order zero delay low pass Butterworth filter with a cutoff frequency of 20Hz. Data logged in TwinCAT (EMGs, GRFs) were loaded directly into MATLAB. Data from different sources were synchronized by an external trigger signal generated by the TwinCAT master. All online data were also saved for use during offline analysis, which was performed in MATLAB.

Assessment of the outcomes

- The analysis of speed adaptation during over-ground walking and calf-raises relied on the time between peaks of the signals of interest. EMG peaks were times between peaks of muscle activations during a given movement. Peaks were obtained by aggressively filtering the EMG signal with zero delay (offline) and detecting local maxima. Only peaks above a threshold value were considered. Torque peaks were detected in the same manner.

Statistical analysis was conducted using the Wilcoxon rank sum test. The tests were performed for each time variable across different speed categories: slow to medium, medium to fast, and slow to fast.

Moreover, the time of both GM and TA activation peaks and NMBC torque peaks along each gait cycle were compared to reference patterns from the literature on intact-limb biomechanics (1).

- The gait training sessions evaluated if the participant could re-learn the timing of peak muscle activations by following reference targets provided to the user via visual feedback (Figure 3). The goal was to give each participant time to adapt his residual muscle activation patterns to be functional for the control of the bionic leg (18). To analyze the results we defined plantarflexion activation peaks to be within the target range if they fell within the mid-to-late stance phase *i.e.*, between 30% and 60% of the gait cycle. Similarly, dorsiflexion activation peaks were considered within the target range if they fell within the early-to-mid swing, *i.e.* between 60% and 90% of the gait cycle. The percentage of muscle activation peaks in the range is determined for each experimental trial.

Correlation values R between GM and TA activation patterns and healthy activation patterns from literature (41) were calculated on Day 1 and Day 3 of the experiment.

- We evaluated the accuracy of the participant in modulating the amplitude of muscle activation peaks and active bionic leg peak torque across all inclinations throughout the entire test duration. EMG and torque peaks were detected in the same manner as previously explained.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Bionic leg volitional control across ground-level treadmill walking speeds

Results showed the participants could always modulate bionic leg peak torque timing across all walking speeds (Figure 2). In this context, we analyzed timing in between consecutive muscle activation peaks (a) and, plantar-dorsiflexion torque peaks (b) throughout the entire test duration (Figures 2-S2).

Overall for the residual GM muscle, the time between muscle activation peaks decreased proportionally to the increasing speeds for the three subjects (see Tables 1-3).

On the other hand, considering the residual TA muscle, the time between muscle activations does not show a pattern with gait speed. Only Subject 2-AMI can modulate the muscle activations proportionally to speed resulting in a decrease of time between activation peaks (see Tables 1-3).

Figure 2. Time in seconds between peaks of muscle activations for GM (blue) and TA (red) (a) and NMBC torques (b), during the walking trial on a treadmill on the second day of experimental sessions of Subject 1-AMI. The average and standard deviation of the time in seconds between peaks of GM activation (c), TA activation (d), and NMBC plantarflexion torque (e) for each different speed and subject.

Table 1. Time between peaks of EMGs and active prosthesis joint torques in the plantarflexion and dorsiflexion directions, for the walking speeds of 1.6, 2 and 2.4 km/h in Subject 1-AMI

Signal	1.6km/h		2km/h		2.4km/h	
	PF	DF	PF	DF	PF	DF
EMGs	1.8±0.2	1.5±0.5	1.7±0.1	1.6±0.3	1.5±0.1	1.5±0.1
Torques	1.8±0.2	-	1.5±0.3	-	1.4±0.2	-

Table 2. Time between peaks of EMGs and active prosthesis joint torques in the plantarflexion and dorsiflexion directions, for the walking speeds of 1.98, 2.34 and 2.69 km/h in Subject 2-AMI

Signal	1.98km/h		2.34km/h		2.69km/h	
	PF	DF	PF	DF	PF	DF
EMGs	1.8±0.2	1.9±1	1.7±0.1	1.8±0.7	1.5±0.1	1.7±0.7
Torques	1.7±1.2	-	1.8±0.7	-	1.5±0.8	-

Figure 2c displays observed modulations in muscle activation patterns. During the 1.6km/h speed condition, Subject 1-AMI progressively adjusted step duration to gradually reduce step time, thereby leading to muscle activation timings at the end of the walking trial more similar to those observed during self-selected speed (2km/h, Figure 2a-b) *i.e.*, step duration transitioned from 1.93s at the beginning of the trial, to 1.56s at the end. In contrast, Subjects 2-AMI and 3-BAP showed a more distinctive step duration across speeds: step duration transitioned from 2.1 s to 1.7 s and from 1.52 s to 1.31 s from low to fast speed, respectively. Figure S2 shows the observed variations in muscle activation patterns and joint torques for these two subjects. During the trials, all subjects activated each muscle multiple times throughout the gait cycle, leading to secondary activation peaks and resulting in outliers with short intervals (Figures 2a-S2), consequently pushing the average time between peaks to a lower value than expected (Figures 2a-S2). Peak activations for both GM and TA manifested within phases of the gait cycle that were comparable to what was observed in the literature from intact-limbed individuals (1). Considering Subject 1-AMI peak GM activations were located at an average of 42.5% within the gait cycle, while TA activations were located at 81.3 %. Similarly, Subject 2-AMI showed peak GM activations at 39.5% and peak TA activations at 60% of the gait cycle. In contrast, peak GM activations of Subject 3-BAP were located at 59.9% within the gait cycle, and, peak TA activations were located at 62.6%. .5±0.3 and 0.2±0.1 for the speed of 3.24 km/h and 0.5±0.2 and 0.1±0.1 for the speed of 3.96km/h, therefore increasing as the speed diverges from the self-selected pace of 2km/h. The peak NMBC torques manifested at 47.6±11.8, 46.0±13.1, and 49.1±11.0%; 40±15, 41.0±14.9, and 38±20.0%; 65.5±5.2, 61.8±17.3, and 66.5±17.6% of the gait cycle for the increasing walking speeds, for Subject 1-AMI, Subject 2-AMI and, Subject 3-BAP respectively. Decoded torques were limited to 50 or 70 Nm as a safety measure for bionic leg control (more details in Section Methods-Online Data Processing Pipeline), which in turn resulted in a flat section in the torque profiles of Figure 4.

3.2 Gait training via muscle visual feedback

Figure 3 describes the evolution of peak activations for each subject, from the first trial to a consecutive one which shows the best performance achieved during the 3 days of the experiment. The plots in the first 2 rows of Figure 3 show the percentage of activation peaks for the GM muscle. Regarding Subject 1-AMI, the peaks within the target range increased significantly from 33% (day 1, trial 1-EMPOWER OFF) to 79% (day 2, trial 1-EMPOWER OFF), to then decrease again to 47% (day 2, trial 2-EMPOWER OFF). On day 3, training was performed with the bionic leg powered ON. The percentage of peaks within the target range increased rapidly, starting at 69% (day 3, trial 1) to then reaching 95% (day 3, trial 2). Similarly for Subject 2-AMI, the peaks within the target range increased from 51% (day 1, trial 1-EMPOWER OFF) to 79% (day 2, trial 1-EMPOWER ON), to then decrease again to 52% (day 3,

Figure 3. The figure contains pairs of graphs for the three subjects: histograms and scatter plots. Each pair represents one locomotion trial. The top pair presents data from the GM, and the bottom pair illustrates data from the TA. Visual feedback was provided in the first 2 days of experiments, and the prosthesis was powered OFF on the first day for all the participants. On the last day, visual feedback was not provided and the prosthesis was powered ON. Scatter plots contain the percentage of the gait cycle where peaks of EMG activations of *gastrocnemius medialis* (GM) and *tibialis anterior* (TA) occur for each gait cycle in a given trial. The x-axis represents the normalized trial duration. The blue-shaded areas highlight the region where peak activations of healthy gait patterns lie (within 30% and 60% for GM and between 60% and 95% for TA). The light blue squares indicate that the peak activation occurs within the expected range, while the dark blue triangles lie outside that range. Histograms illustrate the percentage of peaks of activations that lie within expected ranges for each decile of the trial duration.

Table 3. Time between peaks of EMGs and active prosthesis joint torques in the plantarflexion and dorsiflexion directions, for the walking speeds of 1.6, 2 and 2.4 km/h in Subject 3-OI

Signal	2.52km/h		3.24km/h		3.96km/h	
	PF	DF	PF	DF	PF	DF
EMGs	1.6±0.8	1.7±1.6	1.5±1.2	1.5±0.8	1.4±0.8	1.5±0.8
Torques	1.5±0.8	-	1.3±0.6	-	1.2±0.7	-

trial 1). On day 3 the percentage of peaks within the target range increased from 59% to then reaching 79% (day 3, trial 3).

Finally considering Subject 3-BAP, the peaks within the target range increased from 39% (day 1, trial 1-EMPOWER OFF) to 94% (day 1, trial 5-EMPOWER ON). On day 3, the percentage of peaks within the target range decreased compared to day 1 reaching an average of 21%.

The mean value of GM peak activation for the three subjects stabilized at 48% of the gait phase, which was within the acceptable range for a symmetric walking pattern (18).

The last 2 rows of Figure 3 show the percentage of peaks within the target range for the TA muscle.

Results for Subject 1-AMI showed that peaks within the target range increased significantly from 49% (day 1, trial 1-EMPOWER OFF) to 96% (day 2, trial 1-EMPOWER OFF), to then decrease again to 81% (day 2, trial 2) for TA. On day 3, results showed that the percentage of peaks within the target range increased, starting at 90% (day 3, trial 1) to then reaching 95% (day 3, trial 2).

In contrast for Subject 2-AMI, the peaks within the target range decreased from 99% (day 1, trial 1-EMPOWER OFF) to 45% (day 2, trial 1-EMPOWER ON), to then increase again to 92% (day 3, trial 1-EMPOWER ON). On day 3 the percentage of peaks within the target range decreased from 92% to then reaching 88% (day 3, trial 3).

Finally considering Subject 3-BAP, the peaks within the target range decreased from 95% (day 1, trial 1-EMPOWER OFF) to 7% (day 1, trial 5-EMPOWER ON). On day 3, the percentage of peaks within the target range decreased from 86% (day 3, trial 1) to 53% (day 3, trial 3).

The mean value of TA peak activation for the three subjects stabilized at 73.1% of the gait phase which was within an acceptable range to guarantee enough dorsiflexion that generates sufficient toe clearance (18). Furthermore, for both muscles, within each of the trials, it was observable that the number of peaks in the range tended to rise as the participant got used to that walking condition.

The shape of both GM and TA activation patterns changed throughout the trials, where the GM and TA peak activations stabilized within expected targets (1). Correlation values R associated with healthy activation patterns from literature (41) indicated a change in activation shape across days (see Table S4). Subjects 1-AMI and 2-AMI demonstrated an increase in GM correlation and a decrease in TA correlation, while Subject 3-BAP exhibited the opposite pattern.

3.3 Bionic leg volitional control during treadmill walking at different inclinations

Results showed that Subject 2-AMI and Subject 3-BAP could modulate active bionic leg peak torque amplitude across all inclinations (Figure S3). In this context, we analyzed the amplitude of muscle activation peaks and, bionic leg plantar torque peaks throughout the entire test duration (Tables S2-S3). For the residual GM muscle, the amplitude of muscle activation peaks were (mean \pm standard deviation) 0.32 ± 0.17 , 0.38 ± 0.12 , and 0.38 ± 0.12 and, 0.53 ± 0.29 , 0.23 ± 0.23 , and 0.18 ± 0.28 for Subject 2-AMI and Subject 3-BAP respectively at the ground, 3% and, 5% inclinations (Figure S4).

For the residual TA muscle, the amplitude of muscle activations was 0.32 ± 0.17 , 0.38 ± 0.12 , and 0.63 ± 0.19 and, 0.18 ± 0.12 , 0.25 ± 0.22 , and 0.09 ± 0.13 for ground, 3% and, 5% inclinations, for Subject 2-AMI and, Subject 3-BAP respectively (Figure S4).

Figure S3 displays observed modulations in computed NMBC and active bionic leg torques.

The amplitude of the active bionic leg peak torques decoded by the proposed musculoskeletal model was modulated as a function of walking inclinations. Peak plantarflexion torque values were -29.5 ± 17.4 , -37.7 ± 16 , and -40.7 ± 17.1 Nm and, -35.2 ± 23.7 , -14.2 ± 8.2 , and -29.1 ± 26.3 Nm, for ground, 3% and, 5% inclinations, for Subject 2-AMI and, Subject 3-BAP respectively. These manifested at 41.05 ± 14.9 , 40.4 ± 13.9 , and $35.5\pm 12.08\%$; 61.8 ± 17.32 , 59.8 ± 9.95 , and $58.5\pm 8.02\%$ of the gait cycle for the increasing inclination, for Subject 2-AMI and, Subject 3-BAP respectively. Decoded torques were limited to 50 or 70 Nm as a safety measure for bionic leg control (more details Section Methods-Online Data

Processing Pipeline).

3.4 Bionic leg volitional control during calf raise

Figure S5a shows timing distribution between consecutive peaks of muscle activations, bionic leg joint peak plantarflexion torque, and its respective peak velocity during the calf raise test. The 3 tested cadences, 30, 45, and 60 bpm, underlay time between beats of 2, 1.33, and 1s, respectively. Subject 1-AMI was unable to follow the 60 bpm pace.

Timing in between muscle activation peaks decreased with the increasing frequency. Muscle activations and bionic leg plantarflexion torque peak timing never deviated from expected timings by more than 0.1s. That is, average and standard deviations of time in between muscle activation peaks were 2 ± 0.1 , 1.4 ± 0.1 for the 30 and 45 bpm, respectively; average and standard deviations of time in between plantarflexion torque peaks were 2 ± 0.5 , 1.4 ± 0.1 for the 30 and 45 bpm, respectively (Table S1). Peak plantarflexion joint velocity displayed average timings of $2.7 \pm 3.5s$ and $1.6 \pm 1.2s$ for the 45bpm and 30bpm cadences respectively. Timing deviations in joint velocity peaks were contaminated by one outlier lying at 20s for the 30 bpm cadence, and at 8.5s for the 45bpm trial (Figure S5a bottom histogram).

Table S1 shows a comprehensive overview of timing values.

Figure S5 illustrates GM and TA muscle activations (b and c), respectively, joint plantarflexion torques (d) and ankle plantarflexion angles (e) during bionic leg trial during calf-raise.

The amplitude of the peak activation of TA and GM translated into comparable modulations in torque (d) and joint angles (e).

4 DISCUSSION

We presented a paradigm of human-machine interfacing, where the information extracted from an individual's neuromusculoskeletal system (*i.e.* from measured muscle activations to decoded phantom ankle joint mechanics, Figures 2-4) was used to enable volitional control of a motorized bionic leg (Videos S1 to S9). We tested this paradigm in two individuals with transtibial amputation who underwent the AMI surgical procedures and in one additional BAP individual with transtibial amputation.

Differently from previous work, this study proposed the development of a myoelectric model-based control framework (NMBC) that enabled continuous and volitional control of a bionic leg in uni-lateral transtibial amputees with AMI and BAP amputations respectively. This provides evidence that the proposed NMBC framework, not only enables myoelectric control across a range of movements (*i.e.*, three walking speeds, three ground inclinations, and two calf rise paces), but also across amputations types never compared before within a single study *i.e.*, AMI and BAP procedures. Importantly, the proposed NMBC involved no use of finite-state machines, thereby assuring full continuous and volitional control (Figure 4). Unlike previous literature, the proposed NMBC incorporated a digital twin of the participant's phantom leg that was numerically built to match the anthropometry, musculoskeletal geometry, and force-generating capacity of the participant's intact leg (10; 31). This provides a systematic way of establishing EMG-driven musculoskeletal phantom limb model, differently from previously proposed, heuristically based approaches, where musculoskeletal model's internal parameters were not numerically identified directly from the amputee's residual musculoskeletal system (21; 18; 22; 7).

In intact humans, biological joint torque peaks are volitionally modulated in both amplitude and timing across different walking speeds (1). At high walking speeds, gait cycle duration can be less than 1.5s (42). This represents a short time window for precise joint peak torque modulation, which poses challenges for bionic leg myoelectric control. During our proposed walking tests, the ability to control bionic leg peak torque timing volitionally was critical for cyclic and stable gait across different speeds (Figs. 2,4, S2). In our study, results showed that both AMI and BAP participants dynamically modulated the bionic leg torque to movement conditions imposed by the treadmill belt motion for 3 different speeds (see Figure 2, Video S1). For different walking speeds, participants consistently modulated the timing of GM activations 2c, with activation periods becoming shorter as speed increased. Activations of TA followed the same pattern as GM for subject 2-AMI. A difficulty in activating the TA consistently skewed the results of subjects 1-AMI and 3-BAP, preventing TA activations from displaying the expected descending pattern observed in GM. In this context, participants 1-AMI and 3-BAP could volitionally command torque profiles to the bionic leg with decreased timing between plantarflexion torque peaks as walking speed increased (tables 1 and 3), respectively. Subject 2-AMI demonstrated a reduction of torque peak periods between the fastest and slowest speeds but an increase between the slowest and middle speeds.

Figure 4. Averaged Joint torques at different speeds. Solid lines indicate averages and, shaded areas standard deviations of the active prosthesis torques. Dashed lines are EMG-driven NMBC-decoded torques (more details in section Materials and Methods). Each participant performed treadmill walking at three different speeds: slow (red), medium (blue), and fast (green). Normalized gait cycles (x-axes) are scaled by their relative duration.

Torque commands generated by the implemented NMBC arise from the opposing actions of antagonistic muscle pairs, their activation levels, and relative isometric forces. The delayed activations of the TA influenced torque peaks for Subject 2-AMI at a walking speed of 2.34 km/h, causing them to reach higher values and disrupt the expected trend. Nevertheless, our proposed human-machine interface enabled the participant to accurately control the timing of the bionic leg peak torques in a brief time window corresponding to the gait cycle time.

Commanded peak torque intensities exhibited no consistent pattern across subjects. Higher torques were observed when deviating in either direction (both higher and lower speeds) from the self-selected speed for Subject 1-AMI, while Subject 2-AMI displayed the highest torque at the self-selected speed. In contrast, torque decreased with increasing speed for Subject 3-BAP. In intact-limb humans (43), torque peaks increase with speed. However, the onset of joint torque within the gait cycle fell within the expected range for all subjects and speeds.

AMI subjects improved the control of GM when visual feedback of muscle activations was removed, as shown in Table 3. In contrast, Subject 3-BAP showed activation timings matching those expected in over 95% of gait cycles during trials with visual feedback (Figure 3) but showed a significant decline in expected GM activations when it was absent. This suggests that maintaining focus on the movement was essential for his performance. Hence, future studies should explore the inclusion of extended training sessions for subjects with BAP. Looking at the NMBC torques generated (Figure 4), AMI subjects showed fine control of the torque during stance, more gradual, while Subject 3-BAP showed an on-off ballistic behavior.

Subjects 1-AMI and 2-AMI exhibited GM activation patterns comparable to those of intact-limbed individuals (Table S4). In contrast, the bone-anchored participant (Subject 3-BAP) faced challenges in activating GM, with post-training r -values being lower than pre-training values (Table S4). The shape of the activation patterns of TA did not closely align with those observed in intact-limb individuals for any of the subjects.

Walking on uphill slopes is an important activity of daily living that can be challenging for individuals with amputations. Indeed, walking uphill requires an increased range of motion of the ankle joint compared to level-ground walking, increasing the activity of GM and decreasing TA (44).

Looking at the volitional control during walking on an inclined treadmill, both Subject 2-AMI and Subject 3-BAP generated different amplitudes of muscle activations for each inclination. Subject 2-AMI managed to increase the activation amplitude of GM proportionally to the inclinations as shown in healthy subjects (1; 44), the activity of TA also showed an increased activity which is instead not natural. On the other hand, for Subject 3-BAP only TA showed a decreased activity from 3% to 5% elevation (Figure S4) as shown in healthy subjects (1; 44).

Nevertheless, the performance of Subject 2-AMI degraded compared to the ground-level walking, the torque shape resulted to be more irregular may be due to the increased socket pressures at the calf muscles (45). Moreover, co-contractions increased perhaps to create suspension while the prosthetic socket undergoes a higher distraction force from the residual limb during the initiation of swing (46). On the other hand, Subject 3-BAP showed a ballistic type of control as in the overground walking. Co-contractions are reduced in this case.

Calf raise tests showed that Subject 1-AMI was able to volitionally modulate the timing of the bionic leg plantar-dorsiflexion torque when the stump was loaded with the participant's weight, therefore exercising a functional role of weight-bearing and vertical propulsion (see Figure S5, Video S2-S3).

Gait training was demonstrated to be an important step in guaranteeing adequate learning of a new ankle bionic leg for people with conventional amputation (18). However, no evidence in previous literature showed how, and if, a training session should be carried out in the case of participants with AMI, which motivated the inclusion of a training session in our experiments (Figure 3, Section Results-Gait training via muscle visual feedback, Video S5). Our results indicate that the training sessions with visual feedback are likely to help AMI participants improve their performances of GM activation, supporting conclusions from prior studies: individuals with transtibial amputation who underwent both AMI could be trained to generate muscle activations that are functional for torque-based control of a bionic leg (18). However, in our study, the duration of the training sessions of AMI participants was shorter compared to the 6 training trials mentioned in the literature (18). The higher learning rate of this patient group is likely attributed to the combined effects of AMI and TSR surgeries, along with the implementation of a musculoskeletal model-based controller (31). Nonetheless, the training duration was likely insufficient for Subject 3-BAP, who struggled to maintain performance once visual feedback was removed.

Our proposed approach differs from previously proposed model-based control methods in several aspects. In (16), a linear mapping between muscle activations and torques is applied at the prosthetic joint. This mapping was calibrated heuristically at the beginning of the experiments (16).

Resulting decoded torques were applied to a virtual joint which was then simulated in terms of stiffness, damping, and inertia, finally resulting in position and stiffness setpoints to the bionic leg. Such a method would not fully account for the nonlinearities between muscle electrical signals and generated torques, and chosen stiffness and damping values represent a generic participant or were heuristically determined. Similarly, previous work proposed EMG-based ankle bionic leg control based on the modulation of powered plantarflexion (19; 18) and more recently plantar-dorsiflexion (47; 17) with a proportional mapping between measured EMGs and torques. In this, the pneumatic nature of their bionic leg allowed them to set the baseline ankle stiffness. Furthermore, Shu *et al.* (22) drove a neuromuscular model of the amputated leg with surface EMGs. Torque profiles generated as outputs from a reflex-based musculoskeletal model were used as references for calibrating musculoskeletal model parameters in a second step, which in turn was driven by surface EMGs of the stump. However, their approach used such a model only during powered plantarflexion at the end of the stance phase, employing non-volitional impedance control otherwise, thereby restricting bionic leg volitional control to a subphase of the gait cycle. Moreover, in none of these studies, the underlying musculoskeletal model was established to match the anatomy and force-generating properties of the amputee's intact leg.

More recently, (20; 21) utilized EMG signals from an AMI muscle pair (TA and GM) to estimate a target joint position and impedance, while modulating maximum joint torques based on joint angle and velocity (20), akin to the behavior observed in biological joints. The primary distinction from our approach lies in the incorporation of a model for the missing limb and the personalization of the joint to the individual. Musculoskeletal models have been explored for bionic leg control in a few studies (22; 7), where model personalization is typically based on reference data from healthy populations (7) or achieved through simulation environments (22). Our study is the first to introduce a musculoskeletal model that directly replicates the contralateral intact limb of a person with amputation, offering a more individualized and physiologically relevant approach.

Previous literature indicated that the AMI surgery could enable more effective and biomimetic sensorimotor control post-amputation (48), which could promote embodiment and usability of the neural control (11; 5). The fast learning in the training sessions compared to previous work (18), and drastic improvement during bionic leg control (see Figure 3) shown in this study reinforced these findings.

A primary limitation of our study was the involvement of a small number of participants. Further investigation is required to involve a larger population, including individuals with conventional amputations

(as previously done in a participant with conventional trans-radial amputation (31)) as well as those undergoing AMI procedures and BAP. Furthermore, future research is necessary to understand if our approach could be extended to different walking conditions, including ground elevation changes but also movements including ramps, stairs, or out-of-the-lab settings. The need for including a bio-feedback based training session (Figure 3, Section Results-Gait training via muscle visual feedback, Video S5), as documented in prior literature (49; 50), requires further exploration to determine its necessity specifically for AMI amputees compared to other patient groups (18).

The imposed electrical constraints on the bionic leg affected participant performance, as the delivered torques were limited to 50 or 70 Nm, below the physiological expectations for the participant's weight. This was a safety measure implemented due to software constraints. In particular, no measures were in place to prevent the hardware end-stops from being reached during active control, which in turn could cause physical damage to the bionic leg. Such limitation could potentially be overcome by a software-based end-stop. Moreover, the EMPOWER parallel passive spring design limited the ranges of effective active torque control of the bionic leg. Future studies are needed to evaluate the benefit of this type of control while providing higher torques. In terms of utility and embodiment, we recognize the importance of evaluating our technology by assessing user learning rates, cognitive load, trust in the bionic leg, satisfaction, and sense of embodiment. It is, therefore, desirable to include objective and subjective metrics evaluating those aspects in future studies.

5 ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

We wish to acknowledge the contribution of John-John de Koning for his precious support with the bionic leg alignment.

6 FUNDING

This work was supported by the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA) Innovative Training Networks (ITN) H2020-MSCA-ITN-2019 - 860850 - SimBionics (Neuromechanical Simulation and Sensory Feedback for the Control of Bionic Legs) and by the European Research Council (ERC) under the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Program, as part of the ERC Starting Grant INTERACT (803035), ERC Consolidator Grant ROBOREACTOR (101123866) and the Össur and Ottobock Research Trust Fund at the University of Iceland - Closed loop control of a powered ankle prosthesis using neuromusculoskeletal modelling and artificial sensory feedback (PERSONIFY).

7 AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS STATEMENT

F.D., L.A.G., J.G., G.D., J.S.R., H.v.d.K, and M.S. participated in the design of the study. J.E. performed the AMI amputations and patient recruitment. F.D., L.A.G., and G.D. developed the code used in this work. F.D. and L.A.G. performed the collection, analysis, and interpretation of the data. F.D., L.A.G., G.D., and M.S. wrote the original draft. All authors provided feedback on the manuscript. J.G., G.D., J.S.R., H.v.d.K, and M.S. supervised the research. Project administration and funding acquisition were done by J.G., J.S.R., H.v.d.K, and M.S.. **Competing interests:** M.S., G.D and J.G are co-inventors on EU Patent application WO2022017583A1 filed by Ottobock Se & Co KGAA (DE), University of Twente (NL) and Aalborg University (DK) that describes a method for controlling an orthopedic device that is in relation to the method used in this study. The other authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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